

ISic1571

I.Sicily inscription 1571

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (grey)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Bagliazzo necropolis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte, Baglio Florio
Selinunte

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. οἴμοι ὄ [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284899

EDR 112430

EDCS 41300072

PHI 175684

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.
Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 88

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At B8
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